

Performance Simulation of a 5G Hybrid Beamforming Millimeter-Wave System

Thomas Kühne*, Xiaoshen Song*, Giuseppe Caire*, Kimmo Rasilainen†,
Thi Huyen Le‡, Marco Rossi‡, Ivan Ndip‡, and Christian Fager†

*Communications and Information Theory Chair, Technische Universität Berlin, Berlin, Germany

†Department of Microtechnology and Nanoscience, Chalmers University of Technology, SE-412 96 Gothenburg, Sweden

‡Fraunhofer Institute for Reliability and Microintegration, IZM, Berlin, Germany

E-mail: thomas.kuehne@tu-berlin.de

Abstract—Millimeter-wave systems are the next step to increase the data rate of 5G mobile communication networks. Hybrid analog-digital beamforming is one of the core technologies to enable millimeter-wave communication. Both the theoretical basics and the hardware design have been investigated in recent years. Current research projects like the European SERENA project strive to develop platforms to demonstrate the performance gain of complete systems. We present a simulation based analysis of a planned proof-of-concept system to evaluate the influence of design decisions and hardware impairments. We use a geometry-based stochastic channel simulator and simulate both certain hardware aspects and signal processing parts. We focus on the signal processing parts directly related to the hybrid architecture used for multi user MIMO precoding like the initial link acquisition and the data precoding. We use our own state-of-the-art algorithms for these parts.

I. INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

With the progressing standardization of 5G [1], millimeter-wave systems are closer to commercialization than ever. Future systems are envisioned to be multi user MIMO (MU-MIMO) with large antenna arrays [2]. The conventional full-digital baseband implementation of MU-MIMO precoding for millimeter-wave systems is too costly and, considering the large available bandwidth, from a technology viewpoint unfeasible [2]. A hybrid digital analog (HDA) structure with a combination of both digital precoding and analog beamforming has been considered to solve this problem.

The millimeter-wave channel has distinct features compared to the frequency range below 6 GHz [3]. It has a considerably larger free-space path loss due to the high frequency. In conjunction with the high path loss, the effective channel above the noise floor consists of fewer paths from fewer scatterers and the impact from blockage is much higher [3]. State-of-the-art systems use smaller cells and large antenna arrays to compensate for these effects and increase the system sum-rate [4]. Following, we will focus our analysis on the scenario of an urban small cell with a diameter of up to 300 m and slowly moving users.

In recent years multiple testbeds and prototypes of millimeter-wave systems have been published demonstrating

Fig. 1. One-stream-per-subarray (OSPS) hybrid transmitter architecture.

certain features and properties [5]. The European research project SERENA (<http://www.serena-h2020.eu/>) currently develops a hardware and signal processing platform for the use in millimeter-wave mobile communication. The goal of the project is to have a proof-of-concept for a 5G system in the 37 GHz to 40 GHz band based on an innovative hardware integration platform. In this paper, we evaluate using simulations the hypothetical performance of a system based on the SERENA integration platform. Compared to more theoretical investigations (e.g. [6] or our previous work [7]), we incorporate additional realistic assumptions on hardware impairments like non-ideal antenna patterns and design parameters like the array size. Furthermore, where possible we use physical layer parameters defined by the 5G standard. We use the QuaDriGa 3-D channel simulator [8] with 3GPP parameters for the millimeter-wave channel.

II. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

As mentioned in the introduction, the described system is part of the research project SERENA. Hence, the simulation and the system design in this paper follow closely the hardware specifications of the project [9], [10]. The hardware design is further described in subsection II-A. The signal processing as described in subsection II-B is adopted to conform with the 5G physical layer specifications.

This work was funded from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 779305 (SERENA). X. Song is sponsored by the China Scholarship Council (201604910530).

Fig. 2. Array configuration of the BS showing the module arrangement.

Fig. 1 shows the structure of the system. It is an implementation of the one-stream-per-subarray (OSPS) type of sub-connected HDA architecture. It consists of multiple subarrays, each of which is connected to a single RF chain. In comparison to a fully-connected architecture, where each antenna element is connected to each RF chain, the OSPS structure requires a much lower complexity in the analog hardware. This reduces the number of phase shifters, amplitude modulators, and interconnections in general. As described in many works in the literature (e.g. [11]), an ideal fully connected system outperforms an OSPS system. However, in [12] we have shown that the performance loss in a realistic setting is marginal and the power efficiency of an OSPS architecture compared to a fully-connected architecture is higher. The power efficiency and the reduced complexity are very important considerations for the hardware design of millimeter-wave systems.

A. Hardware Description

The core part of the hardware design is a fully integrated module in the form of a small printed circuit board. It has one RF port connected to four antenna elements by phase shifters and amplitude modulators. The antennas are on top of the module. The module is designed for time-division duplex (TDD) operation in the 5G frequency band between 37 GHz and 40 GHz. The transmitter part is shown as a block in Fig. 1. The receiver is not shown since we focus on the downlink in this paper. Transmitter/receiver reciprocity, which is required by parts of the signal processing, requires a calibration procedure which is not part of this paper. The hardware simulation is based on the design specifications [9] since the hardware is not yet ready for measurements.

The module incorporates a beamforming chip with four channels. It can optionally have four frontend chips with a power amplifier and a low noise amplifier. The power amplifiers boost the maximum output power per beamforming

Fig. 3. Illustration of a BA training slot using 4 directions at the BS and 1 at the UE.

channel to above 33 dBm. This could enable a large BS cell coverage, possibly larger than common small cells. Since in this paper we focus on the small cell scenario, we simulate the modules without power amplifiers. The maximum output power of the beamforming chip is 10 dBm. In our simulations we include a power backoff of 12 dB for a typical 5G waveform [13] resulting in a maximum output power of a single channel of $P_{o,amp} = -2$ dBm. The beamforming capabilities of the module include phase and amplitude modulation. The phase resolution is 5° within a range of 0° to 360° . The amplitude can be set with 0.5 dB steps in a 30 dB range.

Each of the four antenna elements in the module consists of two microstrip patches with horizontal polarization and a half-wavelength spacing. The two patches are fed with equal phase and amplitude from a single beamforming channel using a power divider. Thus, they can be seen as a single element with a specific (directional) radiation pattern (see Fig. 5 (a)). The antenna was designed at the Fraunhofer Institute for Reliability and Microintegration (IZM). The overall size of the module is half of the wavelength at the center frequency times the number of patch elements in the respective direction. Hence, multiple of the modules can be used together to create larger antenna arrays. Fig. 2 shows the concept and the size simulated in this paper. The module concept simplifies the manufacturing and enhances the RF performance but also gives flexibility in designing a larger array.

In the simulations we investigate an array (Fig. 2) which consists of 4 subarrays connected to $M_{RF} = 4$ RF chains. Each subarray is built with 8 modules resulting in $\hat{M} = 16$ horizontal elements and 2 vertical elements. During the simulation we only consider the horizontal domain and use the vertical elements of a subarray with equal phase and amplitude resulting in a fixed beam in elevation in the broadside direction. The total number of steerable elements in the array is $M = \hat{M} \cdot M_{RF}$ (considering 2 vertical elements in Fig. 2 as 1).

B. Signal Processing and Frame Structure

A critical part of a 5G millimeter-wave system is the signal processing necessary for MU-MIMO, this includes the measurement of the channel state and the precoding. Due to the aforementioned large path loss and the HDA structure of the system a special type of channel state measurement or initial beam acquisition (which we refer to as beam alignment

Fig. 4. Frame structure of the signal processing adopted to the 5G standard for 120 kHz SC spacing (for abbreviations see [1]).

(BA)) between the BS and the UEs is necessary (see [2]). The result of the BA is a pair of beam directions connecting the BS and each UE. We name the direction at the BS as angle of departure (AoD) and at the UE as angle of arrival (AoA). In the data communication phase the BS and the UE use beamforming towards these directions to increase the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and overcome the large path loss.

We use our algorithm proposed in [14] for the BA process. In the BA phase, the BS transmits during multiple training slots different synchronization signals using different multifinger beamforming patterns. A multifinger beamforming pattern points a variable number of beams (fingers) towards different directions. It is based on Fourier-type beamforming with multiple directions active at the same time¹. The BS beamforming patterns are defined as a pseudo random codebook known to all UEs. Each UE uses its own random beamforming patterns but with a different number of active directions. One example of a training slot beamforming configuration is shown in Fig. 3. Please note, that this type of beamforming requires amplitude modulation and hence can reduce the transmitted power depending on the number of simultaneously active direction. The UEs measure the received power for each training slot and run an optimization algorithm to find the correct AoD and AoA pair. The number of required training slots depends on the channel conditions. For a detailed and mathematical description please refer to [14]. The main advantages of our BA scheme are robustness to phase and frequency variations (e.g. Doppler spread) due to the power based measurements, the UE centered processing which makes it independent from the number of active UEs, and the low number of required training slots due to the use of multifinger patterns.

Fig. 4 shows the frame structure envisioned for the proposed system. It is based on the 5G definition for the initial acquisition as described in [1]. We use the configuration with the highest available bandwidth of the standard with a subcarrier (SC) spacing of 120 kHz, resulting in 400 MHz

¹In comparison, in standard phased array beamforming only a single "Fourier direction" is active.

channel bandwidth. During the BA phase the synchronization signal blocks (SSBs) are used as training symbols. One SSB is equivalent to one training slot in the described BA algorithm and consists of two synchronization sequences which can be used to estimate the channel power. The encoded information in an SSB can be used by the UE to identify the index of the current pattern from the BS pseudo random beamforming codebook. The 5G initial acquisition structure supports 64 training slots in a 5 ms SSB burst. The BS can transmit every 20 ms an SSB burst to increase the number of available training slots to more than 64. Once a UE has determined an AoD and AoA pair, it feeds the AoD information back to the BS using the physical random access channel (PRACH). The UE transmits the feedback using a single beam along the calculated AoA. During the PRACH phase the BS uses an omnidirectional pattern or sweeps through multiple beam directions to receive the UE feedback. Once the BS has received the AoD information from the UE it can schedule the user in the downlink data communication phase using MU-MIMO precoding as described below.

As can be seen in Fig. 4, in 5G the SSBs use 240 SCs and the data uses 3300 SCs. Within the BA phase of an HDA system the BS can not combine SSB and data SCs since the analog beamforming is independent of the SCs. Thus, the power per SC of a SSB is 11 dB higher than of a data SC improving the measurement SNR of the BA phase.

The path directions in the underlying channel are consistent with the channel second order statistics and vary much slower than the channel small-scale fading [3]. Hence, the data communication phase can be much longer than the BA phase in order to reduce the training overhead².

After the successful BA, a scheduler selects a subset of users for the data communication. The directional nature of the millimeter-wave channel and the HDA system demand a directional scheduler which selects UEs with a required minimum angular separation [15]. We did not include a scheduling algorithm in our simulations but use sets of users with sufficient angular separation for the data communication phase.

During the data communication phase a precoding algorithm is used to transmit data in the downlink to the selected set of users and the acquired beam directions. The algorithm used in this performance analysis is based on our proposed algorithm in [7]. A detailed mathematical description can be found in [12]. We use two variants of the proposed algorithm. One is a pure analog beamforming based version named beam steering (BST) and the other one uses an additional digital baseband precoding based on zero-forcing (ZF). We assume UEs with a single RF chain / data stream. Hence, for both algorithm variants the UE points a single beam towards the acquired AoA. The scheme could easily be extended to support multiple RF chains per user.

²In [3] the authors measured a coherence distance of the second-order statistics of more than 10m. Even with a high speed like 10 m/s (for a small cell scenario) the data communication could use the BA information for up to 1 s.

Fig. 5. Antenna patterns: (a) 3-D view of a single element pattern and (b) example beam patterns of a single subarray for the SERENA array and an array of ideal patch elements.

In the BST case, the BS uses the analog beamforming of one subarray to point a single beam towards the AoD of the UE. The other subarrays point towards different UEs. The data stream for each user is directly connected to the RF chain without any type of digital precoding. The ZF algorithm uses the same configuration for the analog beamforming but adds a digital ZF precoding to the signal processing to decrease the interference between the users. This requires the knowledge of the effective instantaneous channel information. The effective instantaneous channel is the channel seen by the digital baseband after the analog beamforming. This channel has a size of $M_{\text{RF}} \times K$ for K users which is much smaller than the full channel. The common case is to select $K = M_{\text{RF}}$ users. In the case of uplink-downlink reciprocity³ the instantaneous channel can be acquired using uplink signals. In general, the ZF precoding and the effective instantaneous channel acquisition is very similar to the standard full-digital precoding.

Please note, that further parts of the baseband signal processing like e.g. the modulation, time synchronization, and instantaneous channel estimation are out of the scope of this paper. We focus on the parts directly related to the HDA-system approach. The other parts are within the 5G standard relatively independent of the details of the HDA implementation.

III. SIMULATION ENVIRONMENT

To analyze the performance of the described system, we setup a simulation environment based on our own implementation of the signal processing algorithms, EM field simulations of the hardware module, and the QuaDriGa 3-D channel simulator [8]. QuaDriGa is a geometry-based stochastic channel model incorporating among other features like UE mobility, 3GPP channel model parameters and non-ideal antenna patterns.

The radiation patterns of the antenna elements are simulated using CST Microwave Studio©2017 by the Department of Microtechnology and Nanoscience of the Chalmers University

of Technology. The 3-D directivity pattern of the vertical polarization for the element highlighted in Fig 2 is shown in Fig. 5(a). The gain of one antenna element in broadside direction is 8.5 dBi. Two example radiation patterns of single direction Fourier based beams of one subarray can be seen in Fig. 5(b). The non-ideal characteristics of the antenna elements create slightly larger side-lobes and smaller main-lobes compared to a subarray with ideal patch elements. The radiation characteristics of the full antenna array are created using concatenated simulation results from a single module. The simulated antenna characteristics are used at the BS in the QuaDriGa simulator. The UE antenna is set to an array of four ideal patch elements with a half-wavelength spacing.

Unless otherwise specified, we choose the following parameters for the simulations. The center frequency is set to 39 GHz. Other timing parameters are set to the respective values defined by the 5G standard as described in section II-B. The noise figure of the UE receiver is chosen to be 7 dB, which is consistent with the noise figure of the beamforming chip in a SERENA module. The receiver temperature, used to determine the noise power, is 333 K. The BS is 10 m and all UEs are 1.5 m high. The BS array is tilted downwards with an angle of 11.6°. The QuaDriGa channel scenario is set to the values defined in the technical report 3GPP 38.901 [16] (but extended through the QuaDriGa setting `use_3GPP_baseline=0`). In this report the 3GPP consortium standardized channel model parameters for millimeter-wave channels which should be used for 5G system testing. In our simulations we use the urban micro line-of-sight (LOS) parameters.

The users are distributed in a distance d_{UE} between 10 m and 300 m and in an azimuth range of -45° to 45° . The azimuth range is divided into K equally sized subranges with an angular separation of $\Delta_{az} = 5^\circ$. An equal number of users is randomly located in each subrange. The ideal scheduler picks one user of each subrange for the data rate simulation. Due to the 4 subarrays of the SERENA array $K = 4$ UEs are scheduled in one communication slot. During all simulations the UEs have a moving speed of 1 m/s, a slow walking speed. The random walking direction is in the range -45° to 45°

³Which would require a calibration scheme for the described hardware.

Fig. 6. Channel simulation results: (a) visualization of the cell and (b) the average SNR_{BBF} for the BA and data communication phase.

towards the BS. This guarantees that the users always have a LOS channel for a LOS channel simulation.

For the BA simulation we use beamforming patterns with 4 beams (fingers) for the BS and a single beam for each UEs (exactly as shown in Fig. 3). We allow a maximum number of 192 training slots. The result of the BA after the 192 slots is used as input for the precoding algorithm, even in case of an incorrect result.

We do not simulate a complete communication system with for example modulation, channel coding, and synchronization. The focus of the simulation is to characterize the hardware system and the HDA related algorithms described in section II-B. To evaluate the performance of the hardware and the precoding algorithm during the data communication phase we calculate the achievable asymptotic ergodic spectral efficiency [17]. We assume no inter-carrier interference and treat interference by other users as noise. Following, the per user spectral efficiency of the k -th UE is given by

$$R_k = \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{\omega} \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{P_{k,\omega} |\mathbf{v}_k^H \mathbf{H}_{k,\omega}(t) \mathbf{u}_{k,\omega}|^2}{\left| \sum_{k' \neq k} \sqrt{P_{k',\omega}} \mathbf{v}_k^H \mathbf{H}_{k',\omega}(t) \mathbf{u}_{k',\omega} \right|^2 + N_0} \right) \right]. \quad (1)$$

Where $\omega \in [F]$ is the SC index and $F = 3300$ is the total number of SCs. $\mathbf{H}_{k,\omega}(t)$ is the time dependent channel, \mathbf{v}_k is the receiver beamforming, $\mathbf{u}_{k,\omega}$ is the transmitter beamforming and precoding, and $P_{k,\omega}$ is the maximum output power of the transmitter for SC ω and user k . N_0 is the noise power for the SC spacing at a given device temperature including the noise figure of the receiver. $P_{k,\omega}$ is in our setting the output power of a subarray over the number of SCs F and equal to $\hat{M} \cdot P_{o,\text{amp}}/F = -25.14$ dBm for all users and SCs. The sum spectral efficiency for the K scheduled UEs is $R_{\text{sum}} = \sum_{k=1}^K R_k$. This metric does not include the overhead due to the BA and the instantaneous channel estimation, which is required by the ZF precoding scheme. It is an upper bound and will be lower in a real system with modulation and channel coding.

Fig. 7. Average detection probability P_D of the BA for different user distances d_{UE}

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

The cell configuration is visualized in Fig. 6 (a). It shows the LOS power levels in the cell for a BS with a single element antenna transmitting the total output power of the full array and an ideal UE with an omnidirectional antenna pattern. One can see, that close to the BS, $d_{\text{UE}} < 11$ m, the power decreases rapidly. Below this distance the UE is not covered by the main lobe of the BS array. This limit could be reduced by using vertical beamforming at the BS or changing the BS array tilt at the cost of the maximum distance coverage. In Fig. 6 (b) the SNR before beamforming (BBF) is shown for the BA phase (SSB frames) and the data communication phase. BBF means, that the BS and the UEs use a single antenna element with the respective radiation pattern, the BS transmits with the total output power of the full array, and the UEs receive with the given noise figure. The SNR is simulated for the given SC spacing. The curves named “mean” are averaged over all users, SCs, and slots. The “min” and “max” curves are the minimum and maximum values of all simulated users and slots. The data curve is lower than the SSB curve due to the mentioned difference in the number of used SCs.

Fig. 8. Average sum spectral efficiency R_{sum} over the UE distance d_{ue} .

A. Beam Alignment

The performance measure of the BA is the detection probability P_D . It is the probability of finding an AoD-AoA pair between the BS and the UE for which the channel loss is within a 2 dB range from the strongest pair. Multiple pairs can have a similar path loss due to the fact that the BA output is a discrete grid index while the user placement is continuous or because multiple paths have a similar loss in a non-line-of-sight (NLOS) channel. Since we use the simulated BA results as input of the precoding simulation this effect is included in the data rate results. The mean of P_D for all UEs of a given distance d_{UE} is shown in Fig 7. In general, the simulated performance of the BA algorithm is very good. The bad result for $d_{\text{UE}} = 10$ m is due to the mentioned lower distance limit of the main lobe in elevation of the BS antenna. The small cell assumption and the LOS condition⁴ together with the reduced number of SCs of the SSBs is favorable for the BA. $P_D > 0.95$ is achieved for the whole cell with less than 64 slots.

B. Data Communication

To evaluate the data communication performance, we compare the two variants of our precoding algorithm with the sum of the single user spectral efficiency. The single user sum is the interference free upper bound for the precoding results. The average results for multiple user sets vs. the distance of the UEs to the BS is shown in Fig. 8. In the very high SNR region (see Fig. 6 (b), below 100 m) the ZF variant achieves a very high MU-MIMO gain⁵ and has a much better performance than the BST variant. With an increasing distance, the SNR decreases and the BST achieves a similar performance. At the edge of the cell, BST shows a better performance than ZF. This result is consistent with our previous results in [12].

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented an HDA beamforming millimeter-wave system which is currently developed in the European project SERENA. We described the system specifications and the underlying signal processing algorithms

⁴LOS is a typical assumption for millimeter-wave small cell systems [4].

⁵Which means it is close to the sum of the single user rate.

which were previously proposed by us in [14] and [12]. We jointly evaluated the performance of the complete HDA system including the antenna patterns, hardware specifications, and the BA and the data precoding algorithms. We used 5G physical layer frame parameters and the QuaDriGa 3-D channel simulator with 3GPP millimeter-wave channel parameters. The system shows in the simulated small cell scenario a very good BA performance and a good MU-MIMO gain.

Note: for the final paper we will add simulations for NLOS channels. Those results will be obviously worst than the LOS results but still show that such a system can be used in a certain distance range.

REFERENCES

- [1] X. Lin, J. Li, R. Baldemair, T. Cheng, S. Parkvall *et al.*, "5G new radio: Unveiling the essentials of the next generation wireless access technology," 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1806.06898>
- [2] A. F. Molisch, V. V. Ratnam, S. Han, Z. Li, S. L. H. Nguyen *et al.*, "Hybrid beamforming for massive mimo: A survey," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 55, no. 9, pp. 134–141, 2017.
- [3] T. S. Rappaport, G. R. MacCartney, S. Sun, H. Yan, and S. Deng, "Small-scale, local area, and transitional millimeter wave propagation for 5g communications," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 65, no. 12, pp. 6474–6490, Dec 2017.
- [4] M. Agiwal, A. Roy, and N. Saxena, "Next generation 5g wireless networks: A comprehensive survey," *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 1617–1655, thirdquarter 2016.
- [5] R. Gomes, L. Sismeyro, C. Ribeiro, T. R. Fernandes, M. G. Sánchez *et al.*, "Will cots rf front-ends really cope with 5g requirements at mmwave?" *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 38 745–38 769, 2018.
- [6] A. Li and C. Masouros, "Hybrid analog-digital millimeter-wave MU-MIMO transmission with virtual path selection," *IEEE Communications Letters*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 438–441, 2017.
- [7] X. Song, T. Kühne, and G. Caire, "Fully-connected vs. sub-connected hybrid precoding architectures for mmwave mu-mimo," in *ICC 2019 - 2019 IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC)*, May 2019, pp. 1–7.
- [8] S. Jaeckel, L. Raschkowski, K. Börner, and L. Thiele, "Quadrige: A 3-d multi-cell channel model with time evolution for enabling virtual field trials," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 62, no. 6, pp. 3242–3256, June 2014.
- [9] K. Andersson and T. Kühne, "SERENA proof of concept platform and front end specifications," Jun. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3240304>
- [10] I. Ndip, K. Andersson, F. Dielacher, Y. Papananos, J. Reyes *et al.*, "SERENA integration specifications," Jul. 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3240451>
- [11] R. Méndez-Rial, C. Rusu, N. González-Prelcic, A. Alkhateeb, and R. W. Heath, "Hybrid MIMO architectures for millimeter wave communications: Phase shifters or switches?" *IEEE Access*, vol. 4, pp. 247–267, 2016.
- [12] X. Song, T. Kühne, and G. Caire, "Fully-/partially-connected hybrid beamforming architectures for mmwave MU-MIMO," 2019. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1904.10276>
- [13] T. Levanen, K. Pajukoski, M. Renfors, and M. Valkama, "Cost of increased bandwidth efficiency in 5g nr," in *2017 IEEE 86th Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC-Fall)*, Sep. 2017, pp. 1–7.
- [14] X. Song, S. Haghighatshoar, and G. Caire, "A scalable and statistically robust beam alignment technique for millimeter-wave systems," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 17, no. 7, pp. 4792–4805, July 2018.
- [15] V. Raghavan, S. Subramanian, J. Cezanne, A. Sampath, O. H. Koymen *et al.*, "Single-user versus multi-user precoding for millimeter wave MIMO systems," *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 1387–1401, June 2017.
- [16] 3GPP TR 38.901, "Study on channel model for frequencies from 0.5 to 100 GHz," Tech. Rep. v15.0.0, 2018.
- [17] G. Caire, "On the ergodic rate lower bounds with applications to massive mimo," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 17, no. 5, pp. 3258–3268, May 2018.